

The Influence of Social Media Engagement, Consumer Brand Engagement on Satisfaction and Loyalty of Tourists Visiting Coffee Shops in Kintamani, Bangli District, Bali

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ABSTRACT: Bangli is a regency in Bali Province, famous for its natural attractions. Kintamani is quite well known to foreign and domestic tourists, the beauty of the natural panorama of the Batur mountains makes the main attraction of Kintamani tourism destination as a favorite choice for tourists. Currently in the Kintamani area, there are many coffee shops mushrooming along the road, coffee shops in Kintamani in 2020 are 70 locations. With the rapid development of the internet, coffee shop business actors in Kintamani are increasingly aggressively promoting through their respective social media channels. This study aims to determine whether there is an effect of social media engagement, consumer brand engagement on the satisfaction and loyalty of tourists visiting coffee shops in Kintamani.

The research method in this study uses a quantitative approach with a sampling of 200 respondents. The sampling technique in this study used purposive sampling and data collection through distributing questionnaires, observation, and literature study. The data analysis technique uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the SmartPLS 3.3.3 analysis tool.

The results of this study indicate that: (1) social media engagement has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction, (2) consumer brand engagement has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction, (3) tourist satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on tourist loyalty. Social media engagement has a positive and significant effect on the satisfaction of tourists visiting Kintamani coffee shops.

KEYWORDS: Consumer Brand Engagement, Kintamani, Loyalty, Social media engagement, Tourist Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet is the most important innovation since the development of digital media. It combines many of the features of existing media with new interactivity capabilities; thus, it not only changes the way individuals conduct their business with each other but also the way they interact. Since the advent of the internet, travel planning (e.g., travel information search and booking) has always been one of the main reasons people use the internet. The emergence of social media as an all-encompassing platform where users can share ideas, images and experiences has completely changed travelers' behavior in travel information search. Word-of-mouth information posted online through discussion forums plays an important role in the decision-making process rather than tourist attractions or hotel companies directly providing information (rita et al., 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic has implications for all sectors, including the tourism sector. In Indonesia's tourism industry, this virus began to have an impact in early 2020. Social media is now often used in the business world, the utilization of social media makes it easier for us to change the concept of sales which has turned into an online store. This phenomenon is a new way for people to shop in the digital era. Social media accounts such as Facebook and Twitter. Apart from Facebook, Twitter, the fastest growing social media is Instagram (Smith & Anderson, 2018). Travelers often use social media as a medium to share their travel activities (Rukmiyati & Suastini, 2016). Tourists or travelers are known to be active in uploading photos or videos about how they visit an area or tour that they visit.

Bali tourism has changed during the Covid-19 pandemic. This is inversely proportional, which in June 2020 local tourist visits to several tourist attractions in Bali actually experienced an increase in the midst of a pandemic. This increase occurred in coffee shops in Kintamani, Bangli. Kintamani is well known to both foreign and domestic tourists, the panoramic beauty of Lake Batur and the natural atmosphere of the Batur mountains make the main attraction of Kintamani tourism destinations a favorite choice for tourists. However, currently in the Kintamani area, many coffee shops have begun to mushroom along the road, currently

the number of coffee shops in Kintamani in 2020 is 70 locations spread across the Kintamani area (BPS Kab.Bangli 2020). In terms of internet usage, Indonesians are active, especially in terms of online shopping, and social media usage. That 213 million Indonesians already have internet access, everyone has at least 1 mobile device, and Indonesia has a fairly high percentage of social media users, which is 60% of the population, which means there are 3 social media users in every 5 residents. The utilization of social media as a marketing medium has a very promising opportunity for businesses that are run, this is also seen by coffee shop managers in Kintamani.

Social media engagement is a term used to describe consumer involvement in terms of responding to marketing content shared by a social media. Actions that can be seen are such as giving reactions in the form of likes, comments and sharing content with others. Consumer involvement has different levels, some have a low level because they are only content viewers, while those with high involvement are consumers who participate in producing content. Uploading interesting content in the form of photos or videos, invites interest in visiting the platform of the uploaded content, not only visiting digitally, but will lead to interest in visiting directly to the location in the content. This certainly has a big impact on business managers who want to expand their consumer reach and build stronger relationships with their followers. Consumer brand engagement (CBE) is an overall marketing concept that covers different consumers, starting from brand preference and brand purchase (Gambetti, Graffigna and Biraghi, 2012). If explored further CBE is a multi-dimensional construct, beyond the traditional cognitive, emotional and conative dimensions it seems to be rooted in the emerging experiential and social dimensions. Consumer brand engagement (CBE) is a form of consumer psychological condition and their intensity towards a brand, this condition becomes a form of brand affection and participation towards the brand.

Traveler satisfaction refers to the degree of an individual's emotional response when evaluating the performance or outcome of the perceived traveler experience in relation to their initial expectations. Companies in the hospitality sector strive for traveler satisfaction. Traveler satisfaction or dissatisfaction refers to the reaction of travelers to the assessment of the difference between their expectations or performance norms and the actual performance of the product they experience. Uploading a series of promotional activities to attract new consumers and to maintain good relations with old consumers. This is related to the behavior of consumers who feel satisfied so that they can build loyalty. Building attachment with consumers through social media, so that they are increasingly aware of the brands they follow, and indirectly participate in promoting the brands they follow. In addition, loyalty can also be seen by consumers who visit or buy the brand regularly.

For this reason, from the explanation above, it is very interesting to conduct research on how important the influence of social media engagement, Consumer brand engagement (CBE) on the satisfaction and loyalty of tourists visiting coffee shops in Kintamani, in the era of technology which is now growing rapidly, where everything goes viral so that it becomes a future reference in increasing digital marketing at coffee shops in Kintamani.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach, data obtained through distributing questionnaires and direct observation to the research location, namely Kintamani coffee shop. the respondents used were 200 respondents aged 17 years to more than 40 years. then the results of the questionnaire were processed with SmartPLS professional version software to analyze the relationship between research variables. the research variables in this study are as follows: 1) social media engagement, 2) consumer brand engagement, 3) tourist satisfaction and 4) tourist loyalty.

The following is a structural model of the relationship between variables:

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine the effect of the entire hypothesis proposed in this study, both direct and indirect effects. The criteria in testing the research hypothesis can be seen directly or indirectly. Hypothesis testing criteria can be seen through the results of statistical test values and p-values. The hypothesis is declared accepted if the p-value is less than 0.05 and has a statistical value greater than the t table, namely 1.96. Statistical testing is carried out through the bootstrapping method as follows:

		Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CONSUMER BRAND ENGAGEMENT	-> KEPUASAN WISATAWAN	0.379	0.377	0.047	8.085	0.000
CONSUMER BRAND ENGAGEMENT	-> LOYALITAS WISATAWAN	0.196	0.191	0.057	3.465	0.001
KEPUASAN WISATAWAN	-> LOYALITAS WISATAWAN	0.179	0.186	0.075	2.403	0.017
SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT	-> KEPUASAN WISATAWAN	0.600	0.602	0.046	13.040	0.000
SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT	-> LOYALITAS WISATAWAN	0.588	0.585	0.070	8.353	0.000

Some of the research hypotheses proposed in this study are as follows:

Hypothesis 1:

The effect of Social media engagement on satisfaction

H0 : Social media engagement does not affect satisfaction

H1 : Social media engagement affects satisfaction

Test Results:

The first hypothesis tests whether social media engagement significantly affects satisfaction. The test results show that the coefficient value of Social media engagement on Satisfaction is 0.600 and the t-statistic is 13.040. With this t-statistic value, the p-value (0.000) < 0.05 is obtained, which means that the conclusion can be drawn Reject H0.

Hypothesis 2:

The effect of Social media engagement on loyalty

H0 : Social media engagement does not affect loyalty

H1 : Social media engagement affects loyalty

Test Results:

The second hypothesis tests whether Social media engagement significantly affects loyalty. The test results show the coefficient value of Social media engagement on loyalty is 0.588 and the t-statistic is 8.353. With this t-statistic value, the p-value (0.000) < 0.05 is obtained, which means that it can be concluded that reject H0.

Hypothesis 3

The Effect of Consumer Brand Engagement on Satisfaction

H0: Consumer Brand Engagement does not affect Satisfaction

H1: Consumer Brand Engagement affects Satisfaction

Test Results:

The third hypothesis tests whether Consumer Brand Engagement significantly affects Satisfaction. The test results show the coefficient value of Consumer Brand Engagement on Satisfaction is 0.379 and the t-statistic is 8.058. With this t-statistic value, the p-value (0.000) < 0.05 is obtained, which means that it can be concluded that reject H0.

Hypothesis 4

The Effect of Consumer Brand Engagement on Loyalty

H0: Consumer Brand Engagement does not affect Loyalty

H1: Consumer Brand Engagement affects Loyalty

Test Results:

The fourth hypothesis tests whether Consumer Brand Engagement significantly affects Loyalty. The test results show the coefficient value of Consumer Brand Engagement on Loyalty is 0.196 and the t-statistic is 3.465. With this t-statistic value, the p-value (0.001) < 0.05 is obtained, which means that it can be concluded that reject H0.

Hypothesis 5

The Effect of Satisfaction on Loyalty

H0: Satisfaction does not affect Loyalty

H1: Satisfaction affects Loyalty

Test Results:

The fifth hypothesis tests whether satisfaction significantly affects loyalty. The test results show that the coefficient value of Satisfaction on Loyalty is 0.179 and the t-statistic is 2.403. With this t-statistic value, the p-value (0.017) < 0.05 is obtained, which means that the conclusion can be drawn Reject H0.

CONCLUSION

1. Social Media Engagement has a positive and significant effect on the satisfaction of tourists visiting Coffe Shop in Kintamani.
2. Social Media Engagement has a positive and significant effect on the loyalty of tourists visiting Coffe Shop in Kintamani.

3. Consumer Brand Engagement has a positive and significant effect on the satisfaction of tourists visiting Coffe Shop in Kintamani.
4. Consumer Brand Engagement has a positive and significant effect on the loyalty of tourists visiting the Coffe Shop in Kintamani.
5. Tourist satisfaction at Coffe Shop in Kintamani has a positive and significant effect on tourist loyalty at Coffe Shop in Kintamani.

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